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Research Article

**A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY ON THE INFECTIONS OF THE
INTESTINAL PARASITE PATIENTS PRESENTED TO THE
MAYO HOSPITAL LAHORE**¹Dr. Maria Mazhar, ²Dr. Danish Ali, ²Dr. Muhammad Ali Raza¹Govt General Hospital Ghulam Muhammadabad Faisalabad²Medical Officers DHQ Hospital Jhang**Abstract:**

Objectives: The aim of this research work is to conclude the occurrence of the infections due to parasites in the patients referred to the Mayo Hospital Lahore during the season of summer in the year of 2017.

Methodology: Direct examination, concentration of the formalin ether & Ziehl Neelsen staining of the stool samples carried out. For the detection of the SS (*Strongyloides stercoralis*) samples of stools were refined on the medium of the nutrient agar.

Results: Examination of two hundred and five patients carried out. In which 29.75% patients were present with the infection of at least single parasite. The rates of the occurrences were as follows: *Blastocystis hominis* was in about twenty-one percent patients, *Giardia lamblia* was in more than five percent, *Iodamoeba butschelii* was in 0.48%, *Dientamoeba fragilis* & *Trichomonas hominis* has the same rate of 0.48%, *Endolimax nana* was less than one percent. *Enterobius vermicularis* & *Taenia* were also available in 0.48%.

Conclusion: The outcome of this research work involved the importance of the infection of *Giardia* in children with its signs. About seventy-seven percent patients suffering with infection of *Blastocystis* found with symptoms of intestinal infection. Research works in future are required to diagnose the association of *B. hominis* & the signs or symptoms.

Key Word: Abnormalities, *Dientamoeba Fragilis*, *Trichomonas Homines*, Pathogens, Sanitation, Intestinal Infection, Abdomen

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INTRODUCTION:

Parasites are the most common reason for the abnormalities of GI (gastrointestinal) system as diarrhoea, loss of body weight, severe pain in the belly, vomiting, no hunger, the expansion of the abdomen due to pressure & sometimes it causes the abnormalities of nervous system [1]. The infections due to these pathogens are a serious problem to good health in the countries which are under development as well as the areas of tropical & sub tropical regions [2]. Many different factors as poor atmosphere of health, bad social or economic condition, weather & overpopulation of the subjects are the main reasons of the advancement in the occurrence of the infections due to parasites. The discrimination of agents of the parasite is very vital phase for the start of the suitable treatment & elimination of these types of infections. So, appropriate conditions of health in the communities & detection in the early stages are very vital priorities.

The surveys carried out in many countries to know about the development and progression of the diseases which showed that in the season of summer, the frequency of the infections due parasites advances due to increase in the weather temperature & great utilization of the sources of water which are at unhealthy locations with a improper system of sanitation. So, research works on such topics are very vital for the preventions of such diseases. Therefore, there is a priority of research works in the field of GI infections in the countries which are under development. The main objective of this research work is to conclude the frequency of the infections due to parasite in the patients referred to Mayo Hospital Lahore in the season of summer of the year 2017 to help the authorities of the health for the management of the precautionary measures and education to decrease the rate of these infections.

METHODOLOGY:

The samples of the stool of two hundred and five patients who were transferred to the Mayo Hospital Lahore in the season of summer of the year 2017 were gathered for the examinations of the infections due to parasites. A questionnaire completion carried out for each and every patient including data about the age of the patient, gender of the patient, symptoms of the disease & other complaints of the patients regarding the infection. These stool samples were sent to the laboratory of the parasitological issues, located in the School of Public Health in the city of Lahore. Direct view of stool samples through microscope carried out [1] for the diagnosis of the parasites ova, cysts of protozoa & protozoa trophozoite. In the following step, for the concentration of the sample, formalin ether concentration method conducted with respect to the protocol of Garcia [1]. Coccidial discovery carried out with the preparation of the Ziehl Neelsen staining [1], four gram of the stool was placed on the outsider plane of the plate of nutrient agar & sealing of this carried out with the help of parafilm for the sake of avoidance from any contamination. After forty-eight hours & for seven uninterrupted days, the scrutiny for the larva or young type of the nematodes carried out on each plate.

RESULTS:

Faecal samples of two hundred and five patients were evaluated. Ninety-five were the male and one hundred and ten were the female participants. Out of total patients, forty-three were the children having less than twelve year of age and one hundred and sixty-two were adults. One hundred and fifty-five patients found with symptoms of the infection of intestines. The findings showed that sixty-one patients were facing infections due to at least one type of the parasites of the intestines. The infection rate with each type of the parasite is provided in Table-1.

Table-I: Rate of infection with each intestinal parasite (n=205)		
Parasite Subjects	No of Patients	Percentage
B. hominis	43.0	20.970
G. lamblia	11.0	5.360
I. butschelii	1.0	0.480
D. fragilis	1.0	0.480
T. hominis	1.0	0.480
E. nana	2.0	0.970
E. vermicularis	1.0	0.480
Taenia	1.0	0.480
Total	61.0	100

According to the results, the most commonly occurring parasite was *Blastocystis hominis* with a percentage of 20.97. Forty-three patients were found infected with this parasite in which eight were children and thirty-five were adults, total thirty-three 33 patients (76.74%) had symptoms of the infections in the intestines as displayed in Table-2 especially severe pain in the abdomen cavity & diarrhoea. The 2nd most occurring parasite was *Giardia lamblia*, all eleven patients were children having less than twelve years of age & also had the abnormalities of the intestines.

Table-II: Association of intestinal clinical symptoms infected with *Blastocystis hominis* (n=43)

Intestinal B.hominis	B.hominis with symptoms	B.hominis without symptoms	Total
No of Patients	33.0	10.0	43.0
%age	76.740	23.250	100

DISCUSSION:

In this research work, about thirty percent of the study population was suffering from the infections of intestines due to parasites. There was not any

important statistical association between the infections of the parasites & the age or the sex of the patient. The infections due to protozoa were present in very high amount than the infestations of the

helminthes. This is very much similar with the outcome of many studies conducted in various cities of Pakistan which concluded that in current times, the occurrence of the helminthes of intestines had went under an important reduction as compared to the previous old times [2-6]. The parasites of helminthes & protozoa were very frequent as concluded by Rezaeian in 1986 who discovered about fifty-four percent infections of the intestines due to these to parasites (About eighteen percent due to helminthes & forty-five percent due to protozoan parasites) in patients Public Health centre located in Lahore during the three-year period from 1980 to 1983 [7]. In this research work, all the patients of Giardiasis were the children. This is also similar with various works [1, 2] insisting the high occurrence of this parasite in the children & its relationship with abnormalities of intestines in the age group of having less than twelve year of age.

B hominis was present as the most occurring parasite of infection. In a research work of Yazici in 2007 on fifty-eight food workers in the hospital of Aydin of Turkey, same outcome was the finding [8]. In opposition to this research work, Shahbazi concluded 1.6% infection because of *B hominis* on seven hundred and fifty-five patients from the non urban areas of Markazi Province located in Iran [5]. This disparity is because of the groups of the samples which were chosen from the population of same community in the research work of Shahbazi in 2006 [5]. While in recent research work, patients who were referred to the medical institute were displaying the medical symptoms. In the recent research work, in the patients having infection due to *B hominies*, thirty-three patients displayed the medical symptoms. In the research work of Shazly in 2005 on twenty-three patients with the medical signs of *B hominis* was the single agent of the cause of infection [9]. Dogan in 1998 established that all eighty-eight patients with *B hominis* were present with medical symptoms as severe pain in the abdomen cavity & no hunger [10]. But, the infections due to this parasite of *B hominis* are still an under consideration issue [1, 11].

CONCLUSIONS:

The outcome of this research work showed that these pathogens are the main cause of the GI infections in the patients. Research works in the future with large amount of samples, particularly in the patients who are infected with these parasites without having any other agent of the infection, will enhance our

awareness about the association of the infection *B hominis* & supplementary medical symptoms.

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